

This is the list of KAOS extensions analysed by the study A systematic literature review of KAOS extensions

1. Cheng, B. H.; Sawyer, P., Bencomo, N., Whittle, J. (2009) A goal-based modelling approach to develop requirements of an adaptive system with environmental uncertainty. In: SPRINGER. International Conference on Model Driven Engineering Languages and Systems.
2. Diaz, G.; Cambrono, M. E.; Tobarra, M. L.; Valero, V.; Cuartero, F. (2006) Analysis and verification of time requirements applied to the web services composition. International Workshop on Web Services and Formal Methods.
3. Gil, A.; Araujo, J. (2009) Aspectkaos: integrating early-aspects into kaos. ACM Electronic Library. Early Aspects. [S.l.]: ACM Electronic Library.
4. Cailliau, A.; Lamsweerde, A. (2013) Assessing requirements-related risks through probabilistic goals and obstacles. Requirements Engineering, Springer.
5. Lamddi, M. A. (2017) Developing dependability requirements engineering for secure and safe information systems with knowledge acquisition for automated specification. Journal of Software Engineering and Applications, Scientific Research Publishing.
6. Semmak, F.; Gnaho, C.; Laleau, R. (2010) R. Extended kaos method to model variability in requirements. Evaluation of Novel Approaches to Software Engineering.
7. Semmak, F.; Gnaho, C.; Laleau, R. (2008) Extended kaos to support variability for goal-oriented requirements reuse. MoDISE-EUS. [S.l.: s.n.], p. 22-33.
8. Ponsard, C., Touzani, M. (2017) Extending Land Administration Domain Models with a Goal Perspective, 3rd International Conference on Geographical Information Systems Theory, Applications and Management.
9. Ledru, Y., Richier, J.L.; Idani, A.; Labiadh, M. (2011) A. From kaos to rbac: a case study in designing access control rules from a requirements analysis. 2011 Conference on Network and Information Systems Security, SAR-SSI 2011, Proceedings, 05 2011.
10. Baresi, L.; Pasquele, L.; Spoletini, P. (2010) Fuzzy goals for requirements driven adaptation. IEEE. 2010 18th IEEE International Requirements Engineering Conference.
11. Faveri, C. D.; Moreira, A.; Amaral, V. (2016) Goal-driven deception tactics design. IEEE. 2016 IEEE 27th International Symposium on Software Reliability Engineering (ISSRE).
12. Arenas, A. E.; Massonet, P.; Ponsard, C.; Aziz, B. (2015) Goal-oriented requirement engineering support for business continuity planning. Advances in Conceptual Modelling. Springer International Publishing.
13. Brown, G.; Cheng, B. H.; Goldsby, H.; Zhang, J. (2006) Goal-oriented specification of adaptation requirements engineering in adaptive systems. ACM. Proceedings of the 2006 international workshop on Self-adaptation and self-managing systems.
14. Hassan, R., Bohner, S., El-Kassas, S., Eltoweissy, M. (2008) Goal-oriented, based formal derivation of security design specifications from security requirements. IEEE. 2008 Third International Conference on Availability, Reliability and Security.
15. Nagel, B.; Gerth, C.; Post, J.; Engels, G. (2013) Kaos4soa -extending kaos models with temporal and logical dependencies. CAiSE Forum.
16. Sutcliffe, A.; Sawyer, P. (2013) Modelling personalized adaptive systems. SPRINGER. International Conference on Advanced Information Systems Engineering.
17. Huang, C.; Sun, J.; Wang, X.; Si, Y. (2009) Role engineering with skaos for systems employing rbac. Networking and Digital Society, International Conference.
18. Semmak, F.; Laleau, R.; Gnaho, C. (2009) Supporting variability in goal-based requirements. IEEE Third International Conference on Research Challenges in Information Science.
19. Dias, A.; Amaral, V.; Araujo, J. (2009) Towards a domain specific language for a goal-oriented approach based on kaos. IEEE. 2009 Third International Conference on Research Challenges in Information Science.
20. Islam, S., Houmb, S. H. (2011) Towards a framework for offshore outsource software development risk management model. Journal of Software.
21. Ahmad, M.; Bruel, J.-M.; Laleau, R.; Gnaho, C. (2012) Using relax, sysml and kaos for ambient systems requirements modelling. Procedia Computer Science, Elsevier.
22. Brunet, J.; Semmak, F.; Laleau, R.; Gnaho, C. (2008) Using variants in kaos goal modelling. International Conference on Enterprise Information Systems.
23. Fredericks, E.M., DeVries, B., Cheng, B. H. C., (2014). AutoRELAX: automatically RELAXing a goal model to address uncertainty. Empirical Software Engineering 19:1466-1501.
24. Baresi, L., Pasquale, L., (2011) Adaptation Goals for Adaptive Service-Oriented Architectures. Relating Software Requirements and Architectures.
25. Sabetzadeh, M., Falessi, D., Briand, L., Di Alesio, S., McGeorge, D., Ahjem, V., Borg, J., (2011) 13th International Symposium on High-Assurance Systems Engineering.
26. Souza, E., Moreira, E., (2018) Deriving Services from KAOS Models. SAC '18: Proceedings of the 33rd Annual ACM Symposium on Applied Computing.
27. Yu, Y., Lapouchnian, A., Liaskos, S., Mylopoulos, J., Leite, J. C. S. P., (2008) Foundations of Intelligent Systems, 17th International Symposium on Methodologies for Intelligent Systems.

28. Islam, S., Houmb, S. H., (2010) Integrating Risk Management Activities into Requirements Engineering. 2010 Fourth International Conference on Research Challenges in Information Science (RCIS).
29. Nakagawa, H., Yoshioka, N., Ohsuga, A., Honiden, S., (2011) IMPULSE: a Design Framework for Multi-Agent Systems Based on Model Transformation. Proceedings of the 2011 ACM Symposium on Applied Computing.
30. Baresi, L., Pasquale, L., (2010) Live Goals for Adaptive Service Compositions. International Conference on Software Engineering.
31. Ahmada, M., Belloira, N., Bruel, J., (2015) Modelling and verification of Functional and Non-Functional Requirements of ambient Self-Adaptive Systems. The Journal of Systems and Software.
32. Matoussi, A., Gervais, F., Laleau, R., (2011) A Goal-Based Approach to Guide the Design of an Abstract Event-B Specification. 16th IEEE International Conference on Engineering of Complex Computer Systems.
33. Ulfat-Bunyadi, N., Mohammadi, N. G., Heisel, M., (2018) Supporting the Systematic Goal Refinement in KAOS using the Six-Variable Model. In 13th International Conference on Software Technologies.
34. Mihret, B. Z., Jee, E., Baek, Y., Bae, D., (2018) A collaboration policy model for system of systems. In 13th Annual Conference on System of Systems Engineering (SoSE).
35. Kaiya, H., Yoshioka, N., Washizaki, H., Okubo, T., Hazeyama, A., Ogata, S., Tanaka, T., (2018) Eliciting requirements for improving users behaviour using transparency. In Requirements Engineering for Internet of Things.
36. Darimont, R., Ponsard, C., Lemoine, M., (2018) Goal-driven elaboration of OCL enriched UML class diagrams. 18th International Workshop in OCL and Textual Modelling at the 21st MODELS conference.
37. Woldeamlak, S., Diabat, A., Sveinovic, D., (2016) Goal-Oriented Requirements Engineering for Research-Intensive Complex Systems: A Case Study. Systems Engineering.
38. Casagrande, E., Woldeamlak, S., Woon, W. L., Zeineldin, H. H., Sveinovic, D., (2014). NLP-KAOS for Systems Goal Elicitation: Smart Metering System Case Study. IEEE Transactions On Software Engineering.
39. Pasquale, L., Spoletini, P., Salehie, M., Cavallaro, L., Nuseibeh, B., (2016). Automating trade-off analysis of security requirements. In Requirements Eng.
40. Traichaiyaporn, K., Aoki, T., (2013). Refinement Tree and Its Patterns: a Graphical Approach for Event-B Modelling. In Second International Workshop on Formal Techniques for Safety-Critical Systems (FTSCS 2013).
41. Wirasta, W., Soemitro, H. L., Hendradjaya, B., (2016). Utilisation of AHP method in elicitation process for Goal Oriented implementation using KAOS modelling. In International Conference on Data and Software Engineering (ICoDSE).
42. Blackwell, C., Islam, S., Aziz, B., (2013). Implementation of digital forensics investigations using a goal-driven approach for a questioned contract. In Computer Science.
43. Krishnapriya, B, Devi, S., Biswal, D. (2016) Formal Requirements for Microgrid Using Kaos and Reference Architecture. International Journal of Research in Engineering and Science.
44. Ulfat-Bunyadi, N., Mohammadi, N. G., Heisel, M. (2018) Supporting the Systematic Goal Refinement in KAOS using the Six-Variable Model. Proceedings of the 13th International Conference on Software Technologies (ICSOFTE 2018).
45. Postigo, M. A. O., Mertinez, J., Silva, J. R. (2019) Formal Requirements for Microgrid Using KAOS and Reference Architecture 14^o Simpósio Brasileiro de Automação Industrial.
46. Nakagawa, H., Shimada, H., Tsuchiya, T. (2020) Interactive Goal Model Construction Based on a Flow of Questions. Special Section on Knowledge Based Software Engineering.
47. Orellana, M. A., Silva, J. R., Pellini, E. L. (2021) A Model-Based and Goal-Oriented Approach for the Conceptual Design of Smart Grid Services. Machines.
48. Ponsard, C., Ramon, V., Deprez, J.-C. (2021) Goal and Threat Modelling for Driving Automotive Cybersecurity Risk Analysis Conforming to ISO/SAE 21434. Proceedings of the 18th International Conference and Cryptography (SECRYPT).
49. Yin, K., Du, Q. (2021) On Representing Resilience Requirements of Microservice Architecture Systems. International Journal of Software Engineering and Knowledge Engineering.
50. Wang, H., Mitake, Y., Tsutsui, Y., Alfarisi, S., Shimomura, Y. An upgradable product-service system design method based on kaos and time-axis. Journal of Advanced Mechanical Design, Systems, and Manufacturing, v. 18, n. 2, p. JAMDSM0022-JAMDSM0022, 2024.